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Institute of **Physics**

Bulletin of The Environmental Physics Group

Volume 3, No. 2 — Summer 1997

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Editorial.

This edition of the bulletin contains a much longer listing of conferences, etc, than previous editions. We intend to continue this, and hope that you will find it useful. The content of the listing reflects the interests of the editors, and the literature that we are exposed to. There are surely many more relevant conferences that we are not aware of. If you are organising a conference that you would like listed, or are aware of one that you think will be of interest to other readers, please let us know. We can also publish short calls for papers, although we do not want the Bulletin to become dominated by this feature.

This Bulletin also sees a rearrangement of the Committee of the Environmental Physics Group, and the co-opting of a new member — we welcome Dr. Quintin Rayer. We also thank the outgoing officers for all their hard work, on behalf of all of the Committee, and look forward to working with the new officers in their new capacities. The addresses of all members of the committee are printed at the back of this Bulletin. If you have any suggestions, comments or queries regarding the running of the Group, its aims and methods, or any other relevant matter, feel free to contact the Honorary Secretary or any other committee member. And, as usual, contributions to the Bulletin are very welcome — please contact either of the editors.

This Bulletin is available on the internet at the following URL:

http://www.nerc-essc.ac.uk/~dwcp/Htmls/epg_top.html

as is (belatedly) Vol. 3, No. 1. For brevity, the "http://" part of internet addresses is omitted through the rest of this Bulletin. If you would like to receive the full text by email, please contact D. Pearson (dwcp@mail.nerc-essc.ac.uk).

David Pearson, Ranjeet Sokhi (Editors).

The views expressed in this editorial are those of the editors, and do not necessarily reflect those of the Institute of Physics or of the Environmental Physics Group. All contacts, deadlines and dates in this Bulletin should be confirmed and not relied upon. URLs (Internet addresses) are in some instances case-sensitive, in others not so.

The Institute of Physics Annual Congress and EPG AGM, 1997 (at the University of Leeds, 24 - 27 March, 1997).

Report on Environmental Physics at the Congress.

On 26 March a one day meeting on Measuring the Environment took place as part of the annual Congress. Thirty or so attendees heard a wide ranging selection of papers from six invited speakers that comprised an interesting and informative day.

We heard about measurement techniques applied to practical questions about the atmosphere, biosphere, water bodies, and ground water, representing all the major compartments of the environment. The presentations covered novel techniques, such as the use of electrokinetics to determine aquifer permeability and ground water resources and improvements in the routine airborne surveillance of shipping lanes for oil spills and of aquatic contamination of coastal waters. Other papers were about developments in the measurement of rainfall by radar, the measurement of micrometeorological fluxes by observing optical scintillation and satellite remote sensing of vegetation and crops.

The presentations all addressed important needs of society, were of high standard and two at least attracted media interest.

John Garland

Minutes of the Annual General Meeting of the Environmental Physics Group.

University of Leeds, 26 March 1997.

Committee Members present: Richard Clarke
John Garland
Peter Hodgson
Alastair McCartney
Douglas Peirson
Edward Youngs

1. Welcome.

Vice-Chair, Douglas Peirson welcomed the attendees (approx. 30 people) to the meeting.

2. Chairman's and Bulletin Editors' Reports.

Douglas Peirson presented the reports outlining the Group's activities over the last year on behalf of the Chairman and the Bulletin Editors (see pages 4 and 6 below).

3. Election of Officers.

Nominations for the officers of the Environmental Physics Group Committee 1997-98 were:

Chair: Prof. Edward Youngs, Cranfield University
Vice-Chair: Dr. Alastair McCartney, IACR-Rothamsted
Honorary Secretary: Dr. Peter Hodgson, Institute of Hydrology

These members were elected to the posts unopposed. No new nominations for Ordinary

Members of the Committee were received and the existing Committee was re-elected. It was agreed to co-opt Dr. Quintin Rayer on to the Committee.

4. Discussion.

A discussion followed, in which the main point that arose was the rôle of the Environmental Physics Group. In particular the position of the Group in relation to sensitive or political environmental issues was discussed. The majority felt that it was important for the group as a whole to maintain its neutrality, and to contribute by providing the opportunities for scientific discussions on such topics to take place. The meeting was reminded that members were encouraged to contribute articles to the Environmental Physics Group Bulletin in which individual opinions could be expressed. A further point raised was the future format of the meeting at the IoP Annual Congress, in particular how to get more students involved. This will be discussed at the next Committee Meeting.

5. Close.

The in-coming chair, Edward Youngs, led a vote of thanks to the outgoing officers for their sustained and highly valued efforts over the last few years, a factor which has played a large part in the success of the Group.

Peter Hodgson
Honorary Secretary

Chairman's Report, 1996-97

This has been another good year for the Environmental Physics Group. The Committee organised a number of meetings. As part of the 1996 Physics Congress held at Telford the EPG organised a one day meeting on *Physics and the Environment: Processes and Applications*. Also, Professor John Monteith presented one of the plenary lectures titled *What is Environmental Physics?* which generated some controversy. In July a very successful international meeting on *Urban Air Quality* was held at the University of Hertfordshire. In June a few members availed themselves of the opportunity of a visit to Drax Power Station, organised by the EPG. In December the new Headquarters of the Institute of Physics was opened by Her Majesty the Queen. The EPG was asked to mount one of six exhibits on different aspects of how *"Physics Benefits Mankind"* to be inspected by the Queen. I had the honour to man the EPG's exhibit and explained to the Queen how satellite data are being used to provide information required for developing a Water Strategy for Zimbabwe. In February the EPG organised a very interesting half day meeting on *Environmental Physics and Risk in Relation to the Decommissioning of Offshore Platforms* at the Institute of Physics Headquarters.

Again the Education Sub-Committee has had a busy and fruitful year. They are developing a textbook on Environmental Physics that is suitable for sixth-formers and their teachers, to

complement the Environmental Physics module that is now available to some 'A'-level Physics students. After all their hard work it was very gratifying to hear that over a thousand students had opted to take the Environmental Physics module in the first year it was available.

Finally, as I step down from the Chair of the Committee, I would like to thank all the Members of the Committee and particularly the Honorary Secretary, Alastair McCartney, for all their hard work and many useful ideas, which have ensured that the EPG runs smoothly and, I consider, successfully. I wish the new Chairman, Ed Youngs, the best of luck.

John B. Stewart
Outgoing Chair

Comment from the New Chairman.

I have been a member of the Committee of the Environmental Physics Group for six years and take over the Chair now the group has been in existence for seven years and is well established. Being retired from a career in research with the Agricultural Research Council and its successors, I continue my research interests on the physics of water and solute movement in soils and on its applications at Silsoe College, where I am a Visiting Professor in the School of Agriculture, Food and Environment of Cranfield University. Soil physics is just one challenging field of activity in environmental physics. The Environmental Physics Group is for everyone whose activities impinge on any aspect of environmental physics.

A feature of the Group is the diverse interests of its members, each having his or her own idea of what environmental physics entails. Professor John Monteith's considered opinion, as given in his book *Principles of Environmental Physics* and argued in his plenary lecture at the 1996 Physics Congress, is that environmental Physics is "the measurement and analysis of interactions between organisms and their physical environment". That would seem to exclude the processes that form the environment for the organisms and that affect the interactions, but could include some aspects of biophysics. In contrast to John Monteith's definition is that of E. Boeker and Rienk van Grondelle who state in their book *Environmental Physics* that it is "the physics concerning the identification and measurement of environmental problems". There is an obvious difficulty here for anyone enquiring about the subject when two basic textbooks on environmental physics cover quite different topics. The definition given in the Group's introductory leaflet was "the application of the principles of physics to environmental processes and problems", which may be considered by some to be too broad and begs the question as to how far the subject encompasses meteorology, hydrology, oceanography and geophysics. Hopefully a leaflet which has just been prepared by some of the committee members will be more helpful.

It is undisputed that physics has a major rôle to play in solving many of the environmental problems facing the world, and it remains the aim of our Group to heighten the awareness of this, both to members of the Institute and to the general public. Through the Education Group we focus particularly on schools. It is good that many 'A'-level students can now study parts

of environmental physics. The leaflet on environmental physics mentioned above will be distributed to schools with the intention that this will enhance the interest in the subject and an awareness of the possibility of pursuing some aspect of environmental physics as a career.

Over the years of its existence the Environmental Physics Group has organised meetings, mostly jointly with other Groups and Societies where interests overlap. For three years we have participated at the Annual Physics Congress, and this we intend to continue to do, not necessarily every year. For the committee of the Group to arrange useful meetings for our members who have such a wide field of interests, we need feedback, so please communicate your views and ideas to the committee members. Suggestions of subjects for meetings and of speakers are always welcome. The Institute now has a very comfortable Headquarters on Portland Place for members, that houses an impressive lecture theatre in which we can hold our meetings at a reasonable cost. The Group also arranges visits to places of interest — again, suggestions of possible venues are always welcome.

E.G. Youngs
Incoming Chair

Bulletin Editors' Report.

Over the last year several changes have been introduced to the Bulletin. Apart from the change in the format and the name from the 'EPG Newsletter', the editors have encouraged research articles and news/information items from the membership. In this respect we have seen some success and articles are now being forwarded regularly. This we would like to encourage even more. As there is increasing pressure on research organisations to attract more and more external income the editors felt that the Bulletin could help by having a section on 'Research Funding News', covering national as well as international sources of funding. This we hope has been of some help to the membership. In addition to these changes a regular item on the Internet has been introduced to inform the readership of some relevant and interesting WWW sites. By having two editors working together it has been possible to introduce a wider range of topics and this we will continue to do. None of this is possible without the help of the membership and we would like to take this opportunity to pass on our sincere thanks.

Ranjeet S. Sokhi and David Pearson.

Research Notes.

Douglas Peirson* — The Radioactivity from Nuclear Weapon Tests Used as a Tracer of Environmental Processes.

For some decades after 1950 it was necessary to observe and measure the radioactive debris from nuclear weapon explosions, that arrived within the human environment. Knowledge of the quantity and type of radioactivity could be used to estimate the hazard to human beings; that of the distribution in space and time could be used to determine the environmental processes involved and to guide the prediction of effects in the future.

The debris was inserted into the troposphere by smaller explosions and into the stratosphere by the large ones. The radioactivity consisted of a large variety of fission products, having a wide range of decay times, and other radioactive material.

What follows is a historical sketch of the transfer of radioactive material, measured as specific radio-isotopes, from the stratosphere to the troposphere, which are separated by the tropopause ranging from ~11 km above ground level at the poles to ~18 km at the equator. The tropopause, defined as the level where the temperature gradient changes from negative below to zero or slightly positive above in the stratosphere, is a changeable feature exhibiting gaps, particularly at mid-latitude. Then there was fallout onto the land and sea and hence into the biosphere, where the radioactivity was incorporated into plants and animals, and eventually into human beings.

Stratosphere

The radioactive debris injected into the stratosphere, which received the overwhelming proportion, was measured directly, after sampling from balloons and aircraft. Of more importance to the human environment was the behaviour of the radioactivity when it had returned through the troposphere to the Earth's surface. Two significant features have emerged, based upon observations within the troposphere near ground level.

There was a marked peak in the concentration near ground-level of long-lived radioactivity (caesium-137, half-life 30 years) in air and rain each year in the spring [1]. In addition the concentration and deposition of radioactivity (strontium-90, 28 years) in rain peaked at mid-latitude (~40°) with a minimum at the equator [1]. These observations applied essentially to the northern hemisphere where the bulk of the nuclear explosions had occurred. A possible explanation of these features lies in the subsidence of air over the pole in mid-winter bringing the debris into the lower stratosphere. From there it would settle through the tropopause with a preference for its mid-latitude gap.

Two other characteristics of the stratosphere were uncovered by observation of the radioactive debris. Mean residence time in the (lower) stratosphere was ~16 months

* Formerly at the Environmental and Medical Sciences Division, AERE, Harwell. Chairman then Vice-Chairman of the EPG, 1990-1997.

(corresponding to a half-residence time of ~1 year) [2]. Mean residence time against interhemispheric transfer was from 3 to 5 years [2].

Troposphere

The mean residence time in the troposphere was typically one month. This was similar to the transit time around mid-latitudes. The "washout factor" was of the order of 700, expressed as the ratio of radioactivity in equal masses of rain and air [1]. For dry deposition, the "dry deposition velocity" was typically 2mm/sec (for particle sizes less than a micron), given by the surface deposition rate divided by the volumetric concentration in air near ground level.

Of the radioactivity injected directly into the troposphere it was possible to link the trajectories with routine meteorological data [1].

Land (and sea).

The rate of deposited radioactivity exhibited the seasonal and latitudinal variation described above. The accumulated radioactivity could be measured directly or computed from the incremental measurements: the measured amount of global deposition can be compared with the amounts injected into the atmosphere [3].

Biosphere

Plants, animals and humans were exposed to the fallout of the radioactive debris: as with the atmosphere the transfer across interfaces could be studied for the significant fission products. Plants (including foodstuffs) took up current deposition as well as that accumulated in the soil [4] (or water). Animals and humans were exposed to external radiation from the ground, by inhalation of air and by ingestion of food. For humans the content was recorded, with time, of long-lived fission products such as caesium-137 [5] and strontium-90 in bone [6].

Overall, the history of the passage of radioactive debris through the environment demonstrates, quantitatively, the interaction of the various compartments. It is interesting to attempt a simple estimate of the throughput. Thus the total production of (say) caesium-137 in the atmosphere would have been dispersed according to time, season and latitude in the manner indicated. A fraction of the order 10^{-16} had appeared in the human body in the UK by 1970. The radiation dose from this body burden would have been a small fraction of that from the natural content of potassium-40 [5].

References

This is a restricted list of references, chosen for accessibility. However, the citations herein will extend the range of reference.

[1] *Nature*, **205**, 433 (1965).

[2] *Nature*, **216**, 755 (1967).

[3] *Nature* **234**, 79 (1971).

[4] Agricultural Research Council, *Letcomb Laboratory Annual Report*, 1976.

[5] *Int. J. Environmental Studies*, **11**, 83

(1977).

[6] *Brit. Med. J.* **2**, 1225 (1966).

Education.

The GLOBE Programme — Global Learning and Observations to Benefit the Environment.

"The GLOBE Programme is a hands-on environmental science and education programme that joins students, educators and scientists from around the world in studying the global environment.

Age-appropriate GLOBE educational materials have been developed by international environmental educators for use in GLOBE schools. GLOBE teachers attend regional workshops to learn how to teach the measurement procedures, how to use the GLOBE data reporting technology, and how to use GLOBE images as instructional materials. Over 2,500 US schools are participating in the GLOBE programme"

For more information contact The GLOBE Programme, 744 Jackson Place, Washington DC 20503, USA. Email info@globe.gov, internet www.globe.gov/.

The Air Quality Programme of the UK's Atmospheric Research and Information Centre (ARIC).

This covers three main areas: school acid rain surveys; production and distribution of educational resources; and teaching and student supervision in higher education institutes. For full information on ARIC and this programme, contact ARIC, Dept. of Environmental and Geographical Sciences, Manchester Metropolitan University, Chester Street, Manchester, M1 5GD, UK. Tel (0161) 247 1590, fax (0161) 247 6332, email aric@mmu.ac.uk, internet www.doc.mmu.ac.uk/aric/arichome.html.

Research and Other Funding.

Public Understanding of Science — Grants.

Seed grants of up to £3000 are considered twice a year, with an additional round in connection with SET98. Closing dates are 31 October (and 31 March), plus 30 September for SET98 grants.

Development grants of up to £20,000 are considered, but the closing date has passed (30 June).

More information is available from Cheryl Davies, Public Understanding of Science Grants,

Funding

COPUS, c/o The Royal Society, 6 Carlton House Terrace, London, SW1Y 5AG. Tel (0171) 839 5561 x2579.

Joint Research Equipment Initiative — Call for Proposals.

The following ad was published in the THES, 7 March 1997.

There is to be a second joint Research Council/Funding Council/DENI research equipment initiative. The aim is to contribute generally to the physical research infrastructure and to enable high-quality research to be undertaken, particularly in strategic science and technology priority areas such as the generic Foresight priorities. Funds will be made available to support equipment bids to go with funding from other external sponsors of research (e.g. industry, charities, Government bodies). The initiative will be run as two competitions:

Competition A — to fund bids for scientific and engineering research equipment with a total cost of up to £200,000. A sum of £5 million has been set aside for this competition. It is to be funded and run through four of the Research Councils: BBSRC, EPSRC, MRC and NERC. **Applications should be made to the most appropriate of these four Research Councils.**

Competition B — to fund bids for research equipment with a total cost of over £200,000. At least £16 million has been set aside for this competition, which HEFCE, HEFCW, SHEFC and DENI are funding. **Applications should be sent to the most appropriate of the six Research Councils listed below.** In this competition, running costs can be bid for (see guidelines) but the £200,000 threshold applies to the cost of the equipment only.

Both competitions are open to researchers in all UK higher education institutions funded by either a Higher Education Funding Council or the Department of Education for Northern Ireland. Applications will be peer reviewed by the Research Councils. The same proposal may not be submitted to more than one Research Council.

The closing date for receipt of applications is 31 July 1997. Guidelines are available now and should be sought from the relevant Research Council/Funding Council home page on the website. The JREI application form is available from the Research Council home pages.

Contacts are:

BBSRC: Dr. Colin Miles, tel (01793) 413359,
email colin.miles@bbsrc.ac.uk
EPSRC: Mr. John Farrow, tel (01793) 444111,
email john.farrow@epsrc.ac.uk
ESRC: Mr. Martin Kender, tel (01793) 413017,
email martin.kender@esrc.ac.uk
MRC: Dr. Sue Cooper, tel (0171) 636 5422 x6447,
email susan.cooper@headoffice.mrc.ac.uk
NERC: Dr. David Brown, tel (01793) 411797,
email dab@wpo.nerc.ac.uk

Funding

PPARC: Dr. Alan Coates, (01793) 442027,
email alan_coates@pparc.ac.uk

The BBSRC home page is at www.bbsrc.ac.uk/. All other addresses follow this pattern apart from the Higher Education Funding Council for Wales. Its address is www.niss.ac.uk/education/hefcw/.

Support for Scientists from Central and Eastern Europe and the Newly Independent States of the Former Soviet Union to Take Part in Seminars, Conferences, Colloquia and Workshops.

EU money can include the payment of a grant to cover travel and subsistence expenses and enable scientists from these countries to take part in seminars, conferences, colloquia and workshops in Europe, but the subject of the event must be one of the areas covered by the Framework IV Programme. Further information is available from the Mr. Genovese, European Commission, DG XII/B2 — SDME 1/143, 200 Rue de la Loi, B-1049 Brussels. Fax +32 2 296 59 36, email michele.genovese@dg12.cec.be.

ESF Exchange Grants — European Ice Sheet Modelling Initiative (EISMINT).

“Exchange grants are offered during 1997 within the ESF Scientific Programme ‘European Ice Sheet Modelling Initiative (EISMINT)’ to scientists wishing to initiate or to further develop a collaborative project related to EISMINT activities.”

For information on how to submit a proposal, contact Philippa Pirra, EISMINT/European Science Foundation, 1 quai Lezay-Marnésia, 67080 Strasbourg Cedex, France. Tel +33 3 88 76 71 29, fax +33 3 88 37 05 32; eismint@esf.org; internet www.esf.org/eismint or see page 35 of The Journal of the European Science Foundation (ESF Communications), No. 36, April 1997. **The next deadline is 15 October 1997.**

ESF Travel Grants and Study Visits — Programme in Plant Adaptation (1997–2001).

“Grants for short visits for doctoral students and for visits for senior scientists are being offered to enable scientists working in the field of plant adaptation to travel to a laboratory in another European country.” For more information, contact Joanne Dalton, European Science Foundation, 1 quai Lezay-Marnésia, 67080 Strasbourg Cedex, France. tel +33 3 88 76 71 22, fax +33 3 88 37 05 32, email jdalton@esf.org. Or see page 35 of The Journal of the European Science Foundation (ESF Communications), No. 36, April 1997. **The deadline for visits to begin from 1 January 1998 is 1 October 1997.**

Funding

Framework IV: INCO-DC. Research and Technological Development, Including Demonstration, in the Field of Cooperation with Third Countries and International Organisations (INCO): AREA C.

"Area C" is scientific and technological cooperation with developing countries. Relevant sectors are:

- Sustainable management of natural resources
- Sustainable improvement of agricultural and agro-industrial production
- Health
- Information technologies
- Biotechnology
- Materials and Production technologies

Different sectors are applicable in different geographical regions. The full call for proposals is published in the Official Journal of the European Communities, OJ C 117 (15/4/97) pp27-37, Communiqué E21:97.

An information pack on INCO-DC, including application forms, etc., is available from the European Commission, DG XII/B-4, INCO-DC, (SDME), Rue de la Loi/Wetstraat 200, B-1049 Brussels. Fax +32 2 296 6252, email inco-dc@dg12.cec.be, internet www.cordis.lu/cgi/build_doclist.pl

(scroll down to INCO and select "Information package for Part C").

Proposals should be sent by post or courier service to the Commission **postmarked no later than 11 September 1997 (12.00 local time)**, or delivered by hand no later than this date and time at the address given above, or to one of the offices of the Commission, in which case a date-marked acknowledgement will be issued.

Framework IV: INDO-CEE/NIS. Research and Technological Development, Including Demonstration, in the Field of Cooperation with Third Countries and International Organisations (INCO/COPERNICUS): AREA A2.

"Area A" is scientific and technological cooperation in Europe, "A2" is cooperation with the countries of central and eastern Europe (CEE) and the new independent states of the former Soviet Union (NIS). Relevant sectors are:

- Environmental protection
- Environmental and health consequences of ionising radiation
- Health research activities
- Non-nuclear energy (demonstration projects)
- Non-nuclear energy (research projects): fossil fuels
- Advanced communications and telematics applications
- Information technologies

Funding/Events

- Industrial technologies and materials research
- Agro-food: food technology (including food safety)
- Social sciences.

The full call for proposals is published in the Official Journal of the European Communities, OJ C 117 (15/4/97) pp38-40, Communiqué E21:97.

Proposals must be sent to the Commission **before 26 September 1997 at 12 noon, local time**, as confirmed by the postmark, or delivered by hand to the address below or one of the offices of the Commission within the Community by the same deadline, as confirmed by the date of the acknowledgement of receipt. Proposals will not be accepted by fax or email.

Address: European Commission, DG XII/B-2, INCO-Copernicus, Rue de la Loi/Wetstraat 200 - SDME, B-1049 Brussels. Fax +32 2 296 33 08, email inco-copernicus@dg12.cec.be.

Information Technologies (IT) and Industrial Materials and Technologies (IMT): Intelligent Manufacturing Systems (IMS).

Relevant RTD themes are:

- Total product life-cycle issues
- Process issues
- Strategy/planning/design
- Human/organisational/social issues
- Virtual/extended enterprise features

The full call for proposals is published in the Official Journal of the European Communities, OJ C 117 (15/4/97) pp41-42, Communiqué E21:97. Detailed information including a guide for proposers is available from the European Commission, European IMS Secretariat, (N-105 6/84), Rue de la Loi/Wetstraat 200, B-1049 Brussels.

Outline proposals can be submitted at any time up to **21 January 1998**, full proposals at any time up to **21 March 1998 at 12 noon, local time**.

Events, Meetings, Conferences.

EPG Events and visits.

Visit to Alcan Recycling, Warrington, Cheshire.

Date and time of visit: **Friday 24/Oct/97**
3 pm to 5 pm

Events

Alcan Recycling's dedicated aluminium can recycling plant, the first of its kind in Europe, was opened in Warrington, Cheshire, in November 1991. The plant produces ingots from used beverage cans; these ingots subsequently being rolled into sheet at another mill and then supplied to can makers to be made into cans again. With a capacity of over 60,000 tonnes each year, there is enough capacity to recycle all the aluminium cans collected in the UK for the foreseeable future. Alcan's capital investment in the plant alone amounted to some £28 million, of which some £5 million was used to install state of the art emission abatement equipment to minimise the impact on the environment.

To take part in this visit please fill in the form on page 28 of the Bulletin.

Other events in the pipeline — watch this space!

- **Matra Marconi, Bristol:** watch construction of the Envisat Earth-observation satellite in Europe's largest integration facility (necessary because Envisat is as big as a bus stood on end);
- **The Building Research Establishment;**
- **The Transport and Road Research Laboratory;**
- **Environmental Physics Summer School, Summer 1998:** residential meeting for school teachers, EPG Education Sub-Committee and the Institute of Physics.

Other Items of Interest.

Main Society Meetings of the Royal Meteorological Society.

Wednesday Meetings — Normally held at 2.00 pm in Lecture Theatre 1, Blakett Laboratory, Imperial College, Prince Consort Road, London SW7.

- 15 October: Urban Meteorology, organised by Dr. S. Belcher, University of Reading.
19 November: Meeting to coincide with Bjerknes' Birth Centenary, organised by Dr. M.A. Pedder, University of Reading.
10 December: Broadcast Meteorology, organised by Dr. A. Eccleston, The Weather Department Limited.

Saturday Meetings — pre-registration is advised. Contact the RMS to arrange this.

- 15 November: Weather and Aviation Accidents. An all-day meeting in Lecture Theatre 1, organised by Emeritus Professor L. Symons and Dr. A. Perry, University of Wales, Swansea.
25 April 1998: Weather, Climate and Horticulture. An all-day joint meeting with the Royal Horticultural Society in Lecture Theatre 1, organised by Dr. J. Mayes, Roehampton Institute, London.

Events

IGARSS'97 — International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, Singapore, 3–8 August 1997. Title: "A Scientific Vision for Sustainable Development".

IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Society, 2610 Lakeway Drive, Seabrook TX 77586, USA. Tel +1 281 291 9222, fax +1 281 291 9224, email tstein@phoenix.net, internet www.phoenix.net/~tstein/igarss/.

Eighth International Conference on Quantitative Methods for the Environmental Sciences and the Seventh General Meeting of the International Environmetrics Society. Innsbruck, Austria, 4–8 August 1997.

A.H. El-Shaarawi, National Water Research Institute, PO Box 5050, Burlington, Ontario, Canada L7R 4A6. Tel +1 905 336 4584, fax +1 905 336 4989, email abdel.el-shaarawi@cciw.ca.

Summer School: Physical Processes in the Coastal Zone — Computer Modelling and Remote Sensing. University of Dundee, 12–29 August 1997.

Miss S.K. Newcombe, Summer School Secretary, Dundee Centre for Coastal Zones Research, Department of Applied Physics and Electronic and Mechanical Engineering, University of Dundee, Dundee, Scotland, DD1 4HN. Tel (01382) 344933, fax (01382) 345415, email s.k.newcombe@dundee.ac.uk

Global Conference on Environmental Education — "Global Strategy for Sustainable Development through Environmental Education in the 21st Century". New Delhi, India, 18–22 August 1997.

Indian Environmental Society, U-112, (3rd Floor), Vikas Marg Shakarpur, Delhi—110 092, India. Tel +91 11 222 3311 or +91 11 245 0749, fax +91 11 331 7301:

"Forest Policy in Countries with Economies in Transition — Ready for the European Union?" Prague, Czech Republic, 21–23 August 1997.

Dr. Ivo Kupka, European Forest Institute, Tarikatu 34, FIN-80100 Joensuu, Finland. Tel +358 9 1911, fax +358 73 124 393, email kupka@efi.joensuu.fi.

Events

"Space and Electric Power for Humanity" — Fourth Symposium on Space Means for Power Utilities. Montreal, Canada, 24–28 August 1997.

SPS97 General Secretariat, CASI, #818-130 Slater St., Ottawa, Ontario, Canada. Email casi@casi.ca.

Siberian Transect Workshop on Spatial-Temporal Dimensions of High-Latitude Ecosystem Changes, Krasnoyarsk, Russia, 24–30 August 1997.

V.A. Koptyug. Email evag@ifor.krasnoyarsk.su, tel +7 3832 354 846.

Seventh International Symposium on Paleoclimatology. Heiligkreutz/Riedlingen, Germany, 28 August–2 September 1997.

J. Merkt. Fax +49 511 643 3667, email merkt@gatel.bgr.d400.de.

International Geographical Union Regional Conference: "The Atlantic — Past, Present and Future". Lisbon, Portugal, 30 August–2 September 1997.

Prof. Dr. Carminda Cavaco, Centro de Estudos Geograficos, Faculdade de Letras, Alameda da Universidade, 1699 Lisboa Codex, Portugal. Tel +351 1 796 5469, fax +351 1 793 8690, email ceg@mail.telepac.pt.

Fifth Conference on Environmental Science and Technology. Molyvos, Lesvos, 1–4 September 1997.

Prof. Themistocles Lekkas, Conference Secretariat, 10 Aegean Str., GR 151 22 Maroussi, Greece. Tel/fax +301 80 51 824.

Twelfth International Senckenberg Conference: "Muddy Coasts". Wilhelmshaven, Germany, 1–5 September 1997.

Prof. Dr. B.W. Flemming, Senckenberg Institute, Schleusenstrasse 39a, 26382 Wilhelmshaven, Germany. Fax +49 4421 947 5 50, email liebezeit@terramare.fh-wilhelmsaven.de.

Events

Remote Sensing of Coasts and Estuaries, St. Andrews, Scotland, 1–6 September 1997.

Prof. J. McManus, Dept. of Geology, University of St. Andrews, St. Andrews, Fife, KY16 9ST, Scotland. Tel (01334) 476161, email j.mcmanus@st-andrews.ac.uk.

Ninth World Water Congress: "Water Resources Outlook for the 21st Century — Conflict and Opportunities". Montreal, Canada, 1–6 September 1997.

International Water Resources Association, 1101 West Peabody Drive, Urbana, IL 61801-4723, USA.

23rd Annual Conference and Exhibition of the Remote Sensing Society: "RSS97 — Observations and Interactions". University of Reading, England, 2–4 September 1997.

RSS97, Department of Geography, University of Reading, Whiteknights, Reading, RG6 6AB. Tel (0118) 931 8733, fax (0118) 975 5865, email rss97@geography.rdg.ac.uk, internet www.rdg.ac.uk/AcaDepts/sg/Geog/pages/rss97/rss97.html.

Annual Festival of Science. University of Leeds, England, 7–12 September 1997.

Major Events Department, British Association, 23 Savile Row, London, W1X 2NB. Tel (0171) 973 3076, fax (0171) 973 3051.

28th Conference on Radar Meteorology. Austin, Texas, 7–12 September 1997.

Michael I. Biggerstaff, Dept. of Meteorology, Texas A&M University, College Station, TX 77843-3150, USA. Tel +1 409 847 9090, fax +1 409 862 4466.

Includes a special session on Atmospheric Electricity, same place and dates.

William H. Beasley, Committee on Atmospheric Electricity, School of Meteorology, University of Oklahoma, Norman, OK 73019, USA. Email wbeasley@ou.edu.

Events

International Conference on Advanced Wastewater Treatment Processes, University of Leeds, England, 8–11 September 1997.

Zena Hickinson, AE Technology Transfer, Dept. of Civil Engineering, The University, Leeds, LS2 9JT. Tel (0113) 233 2308, fax (0113) 233 2243, email z.hickinson@leeds.ac.uk.

Institute of Physics' "Electrostatics and Environmental Cleanliness". Wednesday 10 September 1997, at the Institute of Physics, London.

Organised by the Static Electrification Group, co-sponsored by the Environmental Physics Group and the IChemE.

Care of the Environment is an issue which is constantly in the news. Legislation and economic pressures are increasing year by year. Electrostatics has an important role in improving the environment. This meeting will provide an opportunity for the exchange of information and ideas regarding electrostatics in environmental cleanliness.

It is hoped that the following topics will be included:

- Precipitation of airborne pollution;
- Removal of pollution in liquids;
- Recycling of used materials;
- Control of domestic pollution — dust, mites, etc.;
- Product/packaging design to inhibit dust deposition;
- Relevant codes of practice and standards.

The deadline for submissions has passed. To register, please contact the Institute of Physics.

European Environment Conference. University of Leeds, England, 16–17 September 1997.

The Conference Manager, ERP Environment, PO Box 75, Shipley, West Yorkshire, BD17 6EZ. Tel (01274) 530408, fax (01274) 530409.

Air Pollution '97 — "Modelling, Monitoring and Management of Air Pollution". 16–18 September 1997, Bologna, Italy.

Helen Fisher, Wessex Institute of Technology, Ashurst Lodge, Ashurst, Southampton, SO40 7AA, UK. Email hfisher@wessex.witcml.ac.uk, internet www.witcml.ac.uk/.

Events

"Business Strategy and the Environment". University of Leeds, England, 18–19 September 1997.

The Conference Manager, ERP Environment, PO Box 75, Shipley, West Yorkshire, BD17 6EZ. Tel (01274) 530408, fax (01274) 530409.

XIII International Symposium on Environmental Biogeochemistry — "Matter and Energy Fluxes in the Anthropogenic Environment". Monopoli, Italy, 21–27 September 1997.

Professor Nicola Senesi, XIII ISEB, Istituto di Chimica Agraria, Università di Bari, Via Amendola 165/A, 70126 Bari, Italy. Tel +39 80 544 2853, fax +39 80 544 2813, email nsenesi@mail2.clio.it.

Conference on Sensors, Systems and Next Generation Satellites III. 22–26 September, London.

Steve Neeck: tel +1 301 286 3017, email Steve.Neeck@gsfc.nasa.gov.

Urban Transport '97 — "Urban Transport and the Environment for the 21st Century". 23–25 September 1997, Perugia, Italy.

Helen Fisher, Wessex Institute of Technology, Ashurst Lodge, Ashurst, Southampton, SO40 7AA, UK. Email hfisher@wessex.witcml.ac.uk, internet www.witcml.ac.uk/.

Third European Conference on Applications of Meteorology. Lindau, Germany, 23–26 September 1997.

Conference Organising Committee, ECAM-97, Deutscher Wetterdienst, Frankfurter Strasse 135, 63067 Offenbach, Germany. Fax +49 69 8062 2488.

Fifth International Congress of the Brazilian Geophysical Society. Sao Paulo, Brazil, 28 September–2 October 1997.

Icaro Vitorello or Antonio Padilha, tel +55 123 25 6784 or +55 123 25 6807, fax +55 123 25 6810, email icaro@dge.inpe.br or padilha@das.inpe.br.

Events

EUMETSAT Meteorological Satellite Data User's Conference. Brussels, Belgium, 29 September– 3 October 1997.

Madeline Pooley, Am Kavaleriesand 31, D-64295 Darmstadt, Germany. Tel +49 6151 807 606, fax +49 6151 807 612.

International Conference on Earth Observation and Environmental Information. 13–16 October 1997, Alexandria, Egypt.

Bashir Saleh: tel +1 203 560 2578, fax +1 203 560 2915, email ruafeng@rusys.eg.net, or Nader Nada: tel +1 730 993 1626, fax +1 703 993 3729, email nnada@osf1.gmu.edu. Internet www.frcu.eun.eg/www/conference/aast.html or www.ceosr.gmu.edu/news.html.

ECOSUD 97 — Ecosystems and Sustainable Development. Castle of Penticola, Spain, 14–16 October 1997.

Liz Kerr, ECOSUD 97, Wessex Institute of Technology, Ashurst Lodge, Ashurst, Southampton, SO40 7AA. Fax (01703) 292853, email liz@wessex.witcmi.ac.uk.

"Monitoring the Oceans in the 2000s: An Integrated Approach". Biarritz, France, 15–17 October 1997.

Internet www.cnes.fr/actualites/OCEAN97/index_uk.html.

10th Conference on Applied Climatology. Reno, Nevada, 20–24 October 1997.

David Easterling, NOAA/NCDC, 151 Patton Avenue, Asheville, NC 28801, USA. Tel +1 704 271 4311, fax +1 704 271 4328, email deaster1@ncdc.noaa.gov.

The First World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) International Conference on Reanalyses. Silver Spring, Maryland, USA, 27–31 October 1997.

International GEWEX Project Office, Suite 1210, 1100 Wayne Avenue, Silver Spring, MD 20910, USA. Tel +1 301 427 2089 ext. 33, fax +1 301 427 2222, email gewex@cais.com.

Events

12th International Conference on Applied Geologic Remote Sensing: "Practical Solutions for Real-World Problems". Denver, Colorado, 17–19 November 1997.

ERIM/Geologic Conference, PO Box 134001, Ann Arbor, MI 48113-4001, USA. Fax +1 313 994 5123, email wallman@erim.org, internet www.erim.org/CONF/FRS.html.

International Conference on Resource Management and Development Strategies. Aligarh, India, 24–27 November 1997.

Prof. Abha Lakshmi Singh, Department of Geography, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh 202002, India.

UN Framework Convention on Climate Change: Third Conference of Parties. Kyoto, Japan, 1–10 December 1997.

UNFCCC Secretariat, PO Box 260 124, D-53153 Bonn, Germany. Tel +49 228 815 1000, fax +49 228 815 1999, email secretariat@unfccc.de, internet www.unfccc.de/index.html.

First International Conference on Asian Monsoon and Pollution Over the Monsoon Environment. New Delhi, India, 2–5 December 1997.

T.N. Krishnamurti, Dept. of Meteorology, Florida State University, Tallahassee, FL 32306-3034, USA, tel +1 904 644 2210, fax +1 904 644 9642; or R.K. Datta, 48 A, Pkt. C, Gangotri Enclave, Alaknanda, New Delhi-1100019, India, tel +91 11 6448155, fax +91 11 4699216.

78th American Meteorological Society Annual Meeting. Phoenix, Arizona, 11–16 January 1998.

There are so many parallel conferences, that we can only recommend the original reference: *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, 78, 557–565-563 (1997).

EARSeL SIG "Data Fusion" Conference. Côte d'Azur, France, 26–31 January 1998.

This conference covers fusion of Earth data: merging point measurements, raster maps and remotely sensed images. Fusion Conference Office, Groupe Télédétection & Modélisation,

Events

Ecole des Mines de Paris, BP 207, F-06904 Sophia Antipolis cedex, France. Fax +33 4 93 95 75 35, email fusion@cenerg.cma.fr, internet www.datafusion.cma.fr/.

GCTE-LUCC Science Conference (Global Change in Terrestrial Ecosystems—Land Use/Cover Change). Barcelona, Spain, 14–18 March 1998.

Will Steffen, GCTE Core Project Office, CSIRO Division of Wildlife and Ecology, PO Box 84, Lyneham, ACT 2602, Australia. Fax +61 1 241 2362, email wls@cbr.dwe.csiro.au.

Environmental Change in Atlantic Islands. Faroe Islands, UK, 16–23 March 1998.

C. Caseldine, Department of Geography, University of Exeter, Exeter EX4 4QJ. Tel (01392) 263263, fax (01392) 263108.

American Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing/Resource Technology Institute 1998 Annual Conference. Tampa, Florida, 30 March – 4 April 1998.

ASPRS, 5410 Grosvenor Lane — Suite 210, Bethesda, MD 20814, USA. Tel +1 301 493 0290, or call the RTI on +1 970 225 3770.

XXIII General Assembly of the European Geophysical Society. Nice, France, 20–24 April 1998.

EGS Office, Max Planck-Str. 1, 37191 Katlenburg-Lindau, Germany.
Email egs@linax1.mpa.gwdg.de.

Third International Symposium on Spatial Accuracy Assessment in Natural Resources and Environmental Sciences. Québec City, Canada, 20–22 May 1998.

3rd Spatial Accuracy Symposium, Centre de recherche en géomatique, 0722 Pavillon Casault, Université Laval, Québec (Québec) G1K 7P4, Canada. Tel +1 418 656 5491, fax +1 418 656 3607, email spatial.accuracy@scg.ulaval.ca, internet www.crg.ulaval.ca.
Deadline for abstracts is 15 August 1997.

Events

Ninth Conference on Satellite Meteorology and Oceanography. Paris, France, 25–29 May 1998.

Marie Colton, Office of Naval Research, Code 321SR, 800 N. Quincy Street, Arlington, VA 22217-5000. Tel +1 703 696 1291, fax +1 703 696 2007.

“Information for Sustainability” — 27th International Symposium on Remote Sensing of the Environment. Tromsø, Norway, 8–12 June 1998.

27th International Symposium on Remote Sensing of Environment, Norwegian Space Centre, PO Box 113 Skøyen, N-0212 Oslo, Norway. Fax +47 22 51 18 01, email and internet isrse@spacecentre.no www.spacecentre.no

Deadline for abstracts is October 15, 1997.

“Hydrology in a Changing Environment.” Exeter, England, 6–10 July 1998.

Dr. Bruce Webb, Dept. of Geography, University of Exeter, Amory Building, Rennes Drive, Exeter, Devon, EX4 4RJ. Fax (01392) 263342, email b.w.webb@exeter.ac.uk.

The Aerosol Society 5th International Aerosol Conference. Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh, Scotland, 13–18 September 1998.

Five parallel sessions are planned, with poster sessions and an exhibition of related products and services. Invited lectures on all the main topics will be given by recognised experts from around the world, and the remainder of the formal presentations will be from submitted papers. A series of workshops and tutorials is also planned.

The submission of papers in the following topic areas is invited:

- Aerosol Physics
- Aerosol Chemistry
- Atmospheric Aerosols
- Indoor Aerosols
- Combustion Aerosols
- Bioaerosols
- Nuclear Aerosols
- Health Related Aerosols
- Ultrafine Aerosols
- Coarse Dusts
- Environmental Effects
- Standardisation
- Gas Cleaning & Separation
- Instrumentation
- Aerosol Generation
- Sampling

Events

There will be a second and final call for papers in the autumn of 1997, and the closing date for receipt of abstracts is **31 January 1998**.

The Aerosol Society, PO Box 34, Portishead, Bristol, BS20 9NR, UK. Tel (01275) 843357, fax (01275) 817428, email admin@aerosol-soc.org.uk, internet www.aerosol-soc.org.uk/.

AMS Conference on Cloud Physics. Everett, Washington, USA, 17–21 August 1998.

Robert Rauber, Dept. of Atmospheric Sciences, University of Illinois, 105 S. Gregory Avenue, Urbana, IL 61801. Tel +1 217 333 2835, fax +1 217 244 4393, email r-rauber@uiuc.edu, internet www.atmos.uiuc.edu/cloud_phys_conf/cloud_phys_conf.html.

Deadline for abstracts is 1 March 1998.

Fifth International Global Atmosphere Chemistry Project Scientific Conference. Seattle, USA, 19–25 August 1998.

Patricia Quinn, NOAA/PMEL/OCRD, Building 3, 7600 Sand Point Way NE, Seattle, WA 98115, USA. Fax +1 206 526 6744, email quinn@pmel.noaa.gov, internet saga.pmel.noaa.gov/cacgp98/.

14th Conference on Planned and Inadvertent Weather Modification. Everett, Washington, USA, 20–22 August 1998.

Tony Grainger, Box 9006 University Station, University of North Dakota, Grand Forks, ND 58202, USA. Tel +1 701 777 3170, fax +1 701 777 5032, email grainger@aero.und.edu. Deadline for abstracts is 5 January 1998.

“Climate and History: Past and Present Variability — A Context for the Future.” University of East Anglia, England, 7–11 September 1998.

Susan Boland, Climatic Research Unit, University of East Anglia, Norwich, NR4 7TJ. Tel (01603) 456161, fax (01603) 507784, email s.boland@uae.ac.uk.

Events/Publications

Workshop on the Assessment of EMEP Activities Concerning Heavy Metals and Persistent Organic Pollutants and their Further Development. Moscow, Russia, 24–26 September 1998.

Marina Varygina, Meteorological Synthesising Centre East, Kedrova str. 8.K.1, R-117 292 Moscow, Russian Federation. Tel +7 095 124 4758, fax +7 095 310 7093.

Offshore Europe 97 — Oil and Gas Exhibition and Conference. Aberdeen, Scotland, 9–12 September 1997.

Val Johnston-Jones, Society of Petroleum Engineers, 4 Mandeville Place, London, W1M 5LA. Tel (0171) 487 4250, fax (0171) 487 4229, email vjohnston-jones@london.spe.org.

ENAMORS — European Network for the development of Advanced Models to interpret Optical Remote Sensing data over terrestrial environments. Tuusula, Finland, 17–19 September 1997.

A workshop to bring remote sensing scientists and decision makers together. ENAMORS, Finnish Geodetic Institute, Geodeetinrinne 2 (PL 15), FIN-02431 MASALA, Finland. Tel +358 9 295 550, fax +358 9 295 55200, email enamors@fgi.fi, internet neutrino.pc.helsinki.fi/jouni/ENAMORS/ws97.html.

Eighth Conference on Mountain Meteorology. Somewhere in the USA, sometime in 1998 — to be determined.

Teddie Keller, NCAR, PO Box 3000, Boulder, CO 80303, USA. Tel +1 303 497 8428, fax +1 303 497 8401, email tkeller@ncar.ucar.edu.

Books, Reports and Other Publications.

***The TIGER's Tale* — Achievements of the NERC Research Programme Terrestrial Initiatives in Global Environmental Research.**

“TIGER was established as a research programme of the Natural Environment Research Council to study global environmental changes at the land surface. TIGER engaged some 300 researchers at 60 different universities and research institutes in its five years of activity at a cost of over £20 million.”

On the cover of this booklet is a beautiful photograph of a running tiger. Two nodes are clearly visible in its undulatory motion: one in the torso, another in the tail.

Publications

Available from NERC, Polaris House, North Star Avenue, Swindon, SN2 1EU. Tel (01793) 411742.

Understanding Our Planet — The International Council of Scientific Unions (ICSU).

For more information or a copy of the brochure, contact International Council of Scientific Unions, 51 Blvd. de Montmorency, Paris 75016, France. Tel +33 1 4535 0329, fax +33 1 4288 9431, email icsu@lmcp.jussieu.fr.

DATA

Radiosonde data, Ozone hole data and ECMWF data are available from the British Atmospheric Data Centre.

For more information, see www.badc.rl.ac.uk/.

The Application of Extended Life Cycle Assessment to Recycling and Waste Management. A Global Environment Change Programme Briefing by J. Powell and A. Craighill. Four pages.

Available from the Global Environment Change Programme, Mantell Building, University of Sussex, Brighton, BN1 9RF. Tel (01273) 678935, fax (01273) 604483, email gec@sussex.ac.uk, internet www.sussex.ac.uk/Units/gec.

Environmental Data — A Key Resource. Catalogue of NERC's data holdings.

The Natural Environment Research Council, Polaris House, North Star Avenue, Swindon, Wiltshire, SN2 1EU. Tel (01793) 411500.

SCOPE Newsletter — Scientific Committee on Phosphates in Europe.

Current issue discusses "The impact of agricultural phosphorus", "How does phosphorus move?", and other things. To get on the mailing list, contact E.C.U. (European Communications Unit), 20 rue de l'Arcade, 75008 Paris, France. Tel +33 1 44 94 80 70, fax +33 1 44 94 81 01, email ecu@net.asi.fr, internet www.asi.fr/scope.

Publications/Other Items/Committee

Free access to journals online.

HEFCE has bought a 3 year licence to IDEAL, the Academic Press online library. If you are a member of a HEFCE-funded UK academic institution, you now have full access rights to this online library. Journals include *Waste Management and Research*, *Theoretical Population Biology*, and many more. For full details of how to login to IDEAL, contact your university's or college's librarian. See also www.janet.ideallibrary.com, or contact S.J Haggis at Academic Press: shaggis@apuk.co.uk.

Other Information.

Send faxes free using the Internet.

This service is available at the following URL, which also contains instructions. There do not appear to be any strings attached, but the fax as received will have an advertisement attached to it. Also, there is a limit on the usage by any user in each hour. [I use it regularly — Ed.]

www.tpc.int/tpc_home.html

The Committee of the EPG.

Chair: Prof. Edward Youngs	9 Roundwood Park, Harpenden, Herts. AL5 3AB. Tel. (01582) 460859 or (01525) 863330, fax (01525) 863001, email e.g.youngs@cranfield.ac.uk
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Committee/Form

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Mr. Peter Hughes	Kingsway College, Grays Inn Centre, Sidmouth Street, London WC1H 8JB. Tel. (0171) 306 5700, fax (0171) 306 5800.
Dr. Douglas Peirson	18 Nuneham Square, Abingdon, Oxon. OX14 1EH. Tel. (01235) 520454.
Dr. Quintin Rayer	LaGuelle, Guellef Road, St. Peter Port, Guernsey, The Channel Islands.
Dr. Neil Roberts	Magnetic Resonance Research Centre, University of Liverpool, Liverpool L69 3BX. Tel. (0151) 794 5629, fax (0151) 794 5635.
Dr. John B. Stewart	34 Twyford Avenue, Southampton, SO15 5NP.
Ms. Alexandra Wilson	Research and Development, Ove Arup & Partners, 13 Fitzroy Street, London W1P 6BQ. Tel. (0171) 465 3045, fax (0171) 465 3669, email alexandra.wilson@arup.com

Form.

Alcan's Recycling Plant, Warrington

I wish to visit Alcan on 24 October 1997. Please send me more details.

Name:

Address:

Telephone:

Email:

Please return this form to: Alexandra Wilson, Research and Development, Ove Arup and Partners, 13 Fitzroy Street, London W1P 6BQ.